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“ODETTE”

It was a stormy Wednesday. The news of a coming storm was heard across town. They say it's going to make a landfall in one of the towns or in the neighboring towns in Southern Cebu. Warnings, announcements, precautions, and many other means to safety were flashed here and there by the local government. Despite this, everyone seemed so calm. Nobody showed any kind of panic, not even concern, as if a storm is not coming its way.

“Nah, I bet it's just one of those ordinary storms which have passed our town. It's not that serious, I bet”, an E-bike driver said.

“Yeah. All that news is just here to scare us! The rain's not even hard, it's just like a shower”, another driver replied. Both of them burst into laughter.

As the rest of the day went by, the rain never really poured harder and everyone thought, “Yeah, it's just like an ordinary shower. Nothing serious is going to happen. Is there?”

All of the townsfolk treated the day just as ordinary as any other day. None of them ever thought of the hurling danger that's coming their way. Nobody listened to the warnings, announcements, precautions, and other safety measures given by the local government. The whole town is willing to shrug this storm off their shoulders.

But as soon as darkness covered the town, something uninvited came with it. People stopped from what they were doing and started staring at their ceiling. That little shower turned into big drops of water almost tearing away every roof in town. Winds started whooshing and whoofing. The town that was once calm has now felt the terror of the storm.

What they thought was just an ordinary storm was no ordinary. It was a super typhoon by the name, Odette.

People might have wanted to scream but no one did, and even if someone dared to scream, nobody will hear because Odette's monstrous wind is louder than ten thousand men screaming.

Tears poured like raindrops but nobody saw because of the darkness. As if the whole town was eaten by a giant monster. The night went by and Odette continued devouring each town it passes. The people who were once composed and unbothered were now trembling in fear and worry. As Odette destroys every home, owners began crying, begging, and praying to God for safety.

Now that same old driver said to himself, “I should've obeyed earlier. I should've listened. If I did, my family and I wouldn't have been entangled with the chaos brought about by Odette. If only I followed the directives from the government, we wouldn't have escaped this storm or prevented it from coming but, if I just listened, as a husband and

as a father, I would've brought my family to safety. And my friend, oh that one dear friend I have, I pray that he and his family were in safety.”

Odette shattered homes all through the night and as soon as the sun shone the first light, everyone sighed a sigh of relief. Everyone in town was safe. Homes, establishments, crops, and livelihood may have been destroyed but families stayed complete. It was never an easy night. It was never an easy storm. It may have brought terror but it left a lesson. Disasters are no joke; thus, it is better to be informed, alert, ready, and safe than sorry.

